

DEVELOPMENT OF CARBON NANOTUBE/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES FOR LIGHTNING STRIKE PROTECTION.

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1. Scientific background.

The last decade has seen much acceleration in the usage of CFRP materials on commercial aircraft. The Boeing 787 “Dreamliner” and Airbus A350 XWB, which are due to enter service within the next few years, are boasting in excess of 50% composite materials by weight [1, 2].

In addition to studying carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, there is a growing focus on the potential effects of nanoparticle reinforcement to further augment the mechanical and physical properties of such materials for use in the aerospace industry [3-6]. These new materials could be employed in a range of novel applications; such as erosion resistance, deicing, structural health monitoring and lightning strike protection.

On average, each aircraft is hit twice a year by lightning [7] with varying degrees of severity, the results of which range from cosmetic to structural damage. A typical lightning strike can deliver an electrical discharge of 200 kA, an impact force of 16 kN and a temperature flux up to 30,000°K (28,000°C) [8].

Lightning strike protection currently consists of bronze woven metallic mesh embedded beneath the paint scheme [2], which acts as a sacrificial layer, designed to ablate during a lightning strike, dissipating the electrical and thermal energy. While this provides excellent protection, it can partially offset the cost and weight saving benefits of using composite materials.

An alternative concept focuses on improving CFRP lightning strike behaviour, by improving the mechanical strength, electrical and thermal conductivity by using carbon nanotubes. While the PAN-derived carbon fibers offer excellent electrical and reasonable thermal conductivity, the epoxy matrix does not, and subsequently isolates and

insulates adjacent bundles of fibers. The theory is to improve the matrix electrical conductivity and possibly to network the carbon fibers both within and between the plies.

In this context, the present study aims to examine the scalability of such physical and mechanical properties of carbon nanotube reinforced epoxy focusing on the effects of nanotube weight fraction and aspect ratio.

The effect of volume fraction on carbon nanotube dispersions has been intensely studied over the years. The effect of carbon nanotube aspect ratio (α) and aggregate size has been investigated, however, to a much lesser extent [6, 9].

With regards to mechanical reinforcement, there is some debate as to the reinforcement effect of carbon nanotubes on polymeric matrices. There are often conflicting claims of carbon nanotubes increasing or decreasing mechanical moduli and the extent of reinforcement effects nanotubes have.

The aspect ratio of carbon nanotubes and the effect on mechanical properties have previously been studied. Critical lengths were identified as a function of the tensile strength and diameter of the nanotubes and the fibre-matrix bond strength, which governed the effective load transfer of the nanotubes, would have on the matrix, given by Eq 1:

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_f d}{2T_c} \quad (1)$$

Where l_c is the critical length of nanotubes, σ_f is the ultimate fiber strength, d is the fiber diameter and τ is the interfacial shear strength.

As well as their effect on the mechanical properties of polymer materials, the potential to use carbon

nanotubes to improve physical properties such as electrical and thermal conductivity have also been explored in great detail. There are few papers, however, that have studied the effect of aspect ratio on such properties.

2. Experimental.

2.1 Nanocomposite preparation

As part of this study, multiwall CNTs without any chemical functionalities were supplied by the Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy at the University of Cambridge (Cambridge, UK). The nanotubes had been produced by chemical vapor deposition [9], and were of good quality. The length and width have yet to be fully characterized, although the average length was found to be relatively long at approximately $50\mu\text{m}$, with a wide length distribution and diameters less than 100nm .

Fig 1: Scanning electron micrograph image of Cambridge nanotubes [10].

The long aspect ratio tubes were left as received, while the shorter aspect ratios nanotubes were obtained by ultrasonication, using a SONICS VCX-750 sonicator with a half-wave extender. The tubes were sonicated in ethanol for 8 hours at 1-hour intervals at 65% amplitude, until the average aggregate length was $\sim 5\mu\text{m}$ [11].

Following sonication the nanotubes were dispersed in 1% SDBS solution and the size reduction of the nanotube aggregates were characterized using a Leica DMI3000B inverted optical microscope.

Fig 2: shows the size variation of nanotube agglomerates following sonication treatments.

From these images, the lengths of the agglomerates were measured using ImageJ and the size distribution plotted (Fig 3). After 8 hours, the mean average length was found to be $5\mu\text{m}$ respectively.

Fig 3: Logarithmic size distribution of carbon nanotube aggregates after sonication.

Carbon nanotubes/epoxy dispersions were produced with weight percentages less than 1%, using Gurit Prime 20LV resin, which is a bis-phenol A epoxy resin, and an aromatic, diamine curing agent.

The nanotubes were added directly to the resin and sonicated. The dispersions were injection moulded between two plates of glass to achieve a good surface finish with desirable uniform thickness. The injected samples were cured for 16 hrs at 50°C . Following this cure cycle, the samples were removed from the mould and were post-cured at 70°C to ensure the sample is completely cured.

Fig 4: shows the injection mould used and the cured nanocomposite specimen.

2.2. Mechanical and physical characterization

Flexural test samples were cut using a diamond saw from the as-prepared samples. All test pieces were in accordance to ASTM D790, measuring $\sim 13 \pm 0.4\text{ mm}$ in width, $3 \pm 0.3\text{ mm}$ thick and 80 mm in length. 3-point bend tests were carried out using an Instron 3343 with a 1 kN load cell. The span

was set at 50±5mm and the crosshead speed was set at 1.3±0.13 mm/min.

The load-deflection curve showed that the sample underwent a yield stress before fracturing before the 5% strain limit, P can be considered equivalent to the yield stress, at the point where the stress-strain curve became non-linear.

Thermal conductivity measurements were carried out using the flash diffusivity technique. In preparation for the test, square specimens, (10mmx10mm), were cut using a diamond saw and coated with graphite. Testing was performed over a temperature range of 50°-200°C using a xenon light flash diffusivity system (LFA 447 Nanoflash, Netzsch Instruments, Inc.) and the thermal diffusivity obtained from the transient thermal pulse using Cowen analysis. The thermal conductivities were derived using the following equation:

$$k = \alpha\rho C_p \quad (2)$$

Where k is the thermal conductivity, α is the thermal diffusivity, ρ is the density and C_p is the specific heat capacity. The density of the samples was measured using the Archimedes method, and the specific heat capacity was obtained using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to perform a modulated temperature procedure, as described in ASTM E2716-09.

Modulated DSC was used to controllably oscillate the temperature program being applied to the test specimen. This method regulates the heat flow into or out of the sample improving the sensitivity of the experiment.

Electrical conductivity tests were carried out using a simple circuit, consisting of a 5 kV voltage source and an ammeter. At lower carbon nanotube loadings, a highly sensitive picoammeter was necessary, as the nanotube concentration increased; this was replaced with a standard ammeter.

Rectangular test samples, 40 mm x10 mm, with an average thickness of 3mm, were cut as with the flexural test samples. A silver-loaded epoxy was used to attach electrodes to the edges. A direct voltage was applied to the sample, and the current response was observed using an oscilloscope. The intensity I through the sample was measured at a

range of voltages, and the bulk resistivity calculated using the following equation:

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{\sigma} = \frac{V}{I} \quad (3)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Thermal analysis and conductivity.

Following the post-curing cycle of the as-processed specimens, a conventional DSC test was used to verify no additional exothermal peak, indicating the material was completely cured.

The results of the modulated DSC tests are shown in Fig 5. The graph shows the modulated temperature rise, illustrated by the sinusoidal temperature ramp, the heat capacity and reverse heat flow. The heat capacity indicates the temperature range of interest, between ~60-80°C.

Fig 5: Modulated DSC profile.

The following equation was used to calculate the specific heat capacity:

$$C_{p_s} = (60 \cdot A_{mhf} \cdot Kc_p) / (A_{mhr} \cdot W_s) \quad (4)$$

Where C_{p_s} is the specific heat capacity, A_{mhf} is the amplitude of the modulated heat flow, Kc_p is the calibration constant, A_{mhr} is the amplitude of the modulate heating rate and W_s is the mass of the test sample.

The results in Fig 6 indicate a significant effect of carbon nanotubes aspect ratio on the thermal conductivity of the composite. The short nanotubes show a modest increase at 0.5% loading. The long

nanotubes, however, show a substantial increase in the thermal conductivity, as much as 78% at 1% loading.

Fig 6: Thermal conductivity data of composite samples.

Han *et al* [12] carried out a review of the work that has been done on the thermal conductivities of carbon nanotubes/polymer nanocomposites. They concluded that the electrical and thermal conductivities should not be treated as analogous. While they both rely on percolation, the difference between the phononic and electronic conduction mechanisms is a significant consideration.

3.2 Flexural strength/modulus.

The flexural modulus was calculated using Eq 2 and the results plotted in Fig 7. The nanocomposite loaded with the high aspect ratio tubes show a continuous reduction in the flexural modulus with increasing loadings of carbon nanotubes. The specimens with the low aspect ratio tubes show a plateau effect between 0.2% and 1% loadings.

Fig 7: Flexural moduli of nanocomposite samples.

It is widely accepted that a reduction in elastic modulus is indicative of poor interfacial bonding

and or agglomeration of the carbon nanotubes in the composite [13, 14], however, Martone *et al* [6, 15] offered an alternative explanation. They concluded that this reduction in elastic modulus and effective reinforcement was could potentially be a result of the interconnectivity of the carbon nanotubes having a detrimental effect on the efficiency of the stress transfer between the particles. They also concluded, with the help of modeling that the effect of nanotube incorporation on the effects of mechanical properties did not behave linearly and therefore could not be described using a simple rule of mixtures.

Fig 8 shows the change in flexural strength with increasing weight fraction of both high and low aspect ratio nanotubes.

Fig 8: Flexural strength of composite specimen containing high aspect ratio carbon nanotubes.

The flexural strength of the samples was shown to increase with increasing carbon nanotubes incorporation. The specimens with the high aspect ratio tubes were found to increase rapidly, before falling. This reduction in the flexural strength between 0.5%-1% loadings could also be attributed to poorer sample quality, with the presence of voids apparent in the sample. The specimens containing the low aspect ratio tubes rose continuously as the nanotubes concentration increased.

In addition to measuring the specific heat capacity, the modulated DSC tests were also used to measure the glass transition temperature (T_g). The reverse heat flow was plotted against temperature, and at the step-wise transition, or enthalpic relaxation region, the T_g was measured. Table 1 outlines the values of the glass transition temperatures at different weight percentages and aspect ratios.

Table 1: Glass transition temperatures.

	Wt% of CNT				
	0%	0.1%	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%
High α	77.63	78.50	76.82	83.61	82.90
Low α	77.63	81.83	69.55	79.09	75.70

These changes in the glass transition temperature indicate that the incorporation of nanoparticles have an effect on the motion of the polymer chains. Warriar *et al* [16] also discussed the importance of interfacial interactions, free volume and changes in the cure cycle, that would all have an effect on the final T_g .

Preliminary tests were carried out using DSC to run and monitor the cure of cycle of the carbon nanotube-epoxy dispersions. The results showed a faster onset of the exothermal peak, which would be expected due to the increase in thermal conductivity. In addition to this, the exothermal peak showed a stronger signal in the nanotube-loaded sample. Both of these findings indicate that the cure kinetics are affected by the incorporation of carbon nanotubes and could be a contributing factor to the change in mechanical properties as a result.

3.3 Electrical conductivity.

The resistivity of the unloaded epoxy could not be fully characterized, as it was found to be too resistive, even at voltages up to 5000 kV. It can therefore be assumed that the resistivity exceeds the order of $5 \times 10^{12} \Omega$.

Fig 9: Electrical resistivity data of composite samples.

The electrical conductivity measurements show that percolation of the long aspect ratio tubes can be achieved as low as 0.1% loading. Between 0.2% and 0.5% the conductivity would seem to plateau. The low aspect ratio tubes take longer to reach percolation and show early signs of beginning to

plateau between 0.5%-1%. This suggests that the shorter aspect ratio tubes will not be able to achieve the same level of conductivity as the high aspect ratio tubes. There variations in conductivity between the different weight fractions can be attributed to the formation of percolating networks and increasing contact resistance, resulting from the increase in connectivity, required to form this network.

Sandler *et al* [17, 18] previously worked on the effect of aspect ratio of carbon nanotubes and the extent to which this impacted on the formation of percolation networks in carbon nanotube-epoxy composites. Despite the fact that these experiments were focusing on aligned nanotubes, to achieve ultra-low loadings of nanotubes, the results in Fig 11 echo their findings, and complement their conclusions that increasing nanotube length appears to delay the onset of percolation as well as the maximum composite conductivity for a given weight fraction.

4. Summary and conclusions.

Sonication has been used to breakdown long aspect ratio tubes to short tubes, and a technique to quickly monitor this size reduction described.

Nanocomposite samples consisting of these high and low aspect ratio carbon nanotubes have been produced at various weight fractions up to 1%. Test specimens for electrical, thermal and mechanical testing have been prepared and tests conducted.

Differential scanning calorimetry has been used to monitor the cure cycle, confirm the extent of curing and measure the glass transition temperature of these nanocomposites materials.

Thermal conductivity results have shown a 78% increase between the unloaded and 1% loaded specimens with high aspect ratio nanotubes. Results from the low aspect ratio tubes show a modest improvement of 7% increase in thermal conductivity at between the unloaded and 0.5% loading.

Results from the mechanical testing have shown an overall decrease in the flexural modulus of the composites with increasing nanotubes weight fraction. The flexural strength of the materials, however, has been shown to increase with both high and low aspect ratio nanotubes.

Electrical conductivity tests have shown a substantial increase in the conductivity at relatively low loadings of carbon nanotubes. The aspect ratios of the tubes have been shown to influence the percolation threshold and the overall current carrying capacity of the composite.

Carbon nanotubes have previously been shown to improve physical and mechanical properties. The effect of aspect ratio on their enhancement and reinforcement potential has still to be fully investigated. It is fair to conclude, however, that due to their ability to improve a broad range of physical and mechanical properties at relatively low loadings, carbon nanotubes are a promising candidate to improve the lightning strike behavior of CFRP.

Continuing work aims to study the effects on carbon nanotube aspect ratio on the rheological behavior to further understand the impact that this has on the processability of the carbon nanotube-epoxy dispersions.

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